

PARAMETERS INTERACTION OF RADIATION VULCANIZED NATURAL RUBBER LATEX (RVNRL) SENSITIZED BY N-BUTYL ACRYLATE

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ABSTRACT

Response surface methodology was utilized to conceive a mathematical relationship between the crosslinking efficiency of natural rubber latex vulcanized by gamma rays, and the process parameters (n-butyl acrylate and KOH). The radiation vulcanization of latex can be optimized at low vulcanization dose (VD) and at high concentration of n-BA. This relationship can be estimated by the following model.

$$\hat{y} = -3.43 + 7.52[n.BA] - 1.07[n.BA]^2 + 1.68(VD) - 0.056(VD)^2.$$

Keywords: *natural rubber, radiation vulcanization, latex, response surface methodology*

RESUMO

Foi utilizada a metodologia de superfície de resposta para encontrar uma correlação matemática entre a eficiência de reticulação do látex de borracha natural vulcanizada com raios gama e os parâmetros de processo (acrilato de n-butila e KOH). A vulcanização por radiação do látex pode ser otimizada para baixas doses de vulcanização (DV) e altas concentrações do acrilato de n-butila. A correlação pode ser estimada pelo seguinte modelo matemático: $\hat{y} = -3.43 + 7.52[n.BA] - 1.07[n.BA]^2 + 1.68(VD) - 0.056(VD)^2$.

Palavras-chave: *borracha natural, vulcanização por radiação, látex, metodologia de superfície de resposta.*

Introduction

The conventional vulcanization process of natural rubber (NR) latex occurs in the presence of sulfur and pollutants [Mausser, 1987] and these are responsible for the production of high cytotoxicity [Ikarashi, 1992] and allergy causing compounds, such as nitrosamines and nitrostable materials, [Niepel, 1990] in rubber goods.

Vulcanization of natural rubber latex can also be achieved by radiation (RVNRL). This state-of-the-art technology has been studied for a long time by a number of countries including France, Poland, India and Indonesia. Among

these countries, France was eager to commercialize the process. However, the RVNRL technique was not used in industries because the high irradiation cost and the low quality products obtained.

The RVNRL became an industrial process when the radiation dose for vulcanization decreased with the use of sensitizers, such as chlorinated hydrocarbons like CCl_4 and chloroform. The process costs thus become competitive and physical and mechanical properties of the latex were maintained. Addition of 5% CCl_4 reduced the vulcanization dose to 40kGy [Minoura and Asso, 1961; Laizier, 1969; Sumarno and Sundardi,

1977]. In fact, this vulcanization dose was still considered to be high in terms of irradiation cost and toxicity level, produced by CCl_4 . Sundardi (1985) and Sutarman (1983) utilized polyfunctional acrylic monomers such as trymethylolpropane trimethacrylate (TMPT) and neopentylglycol dimethacrylate (NPG). Makuuchi et al. [Makuuchi and Hagiwara, 1983; Makuuchi and Hagiwara, 1984; Makuuchi and Hagiwara, 1985; Makuuchi and Tsushima, 1988] and Devendra (1990), utilized polyfunctional and monofunctional acrylic monomers to substitute CCl_4 . Increase in effectiveness of radiation vulcanization of NR latex depends on the solubility of polyfunctional monomers in NR. This solubility in NR increased with high hydrophobicity of polyfunctional monomers. NPG exhibited good vulcanization efficiency and also the monofunctional acrylates such as 2-ethylhexyl acrylate (2EHA) and n-BA. Sabarinah *et al* (1990) discovered that n-BA was the best sensitizer when utilized in 2% amounts. Zhonghai and Makuuchi (1990) confirmed the high efficiency of n-BA. However it was necessary to use it with 0.2% of KOH to stabilize the NR latex. The vulcanization dose was reduced to 10kGy. Aroonvisoot and Makuuchi (1990) used ter-butyl hydroperoxide (t-BHP) as a co-sensitizer and reduced the vulcanization dose to 8kGy, making the whole process more economical. So far, neither a study of the interaction of the parameters of this process, nor a proposal of a mathematical relation to predict the effect of changes in processing conditions have been carried out.

This paper presents a mathematical relationship, showing the interaction and the process parameters effects of RVNRL sensitized by n-BA at room temperature. The parameters studied were: the vulcanization dose (VD), the irradiation dose rate (DR) and the concentration ratio of the sensitizer system $[\text{n-BA}]/[\text{KOH}]$. These were considered as independent variables whereas the tensile strength (Ts) of the rubber produced by the RVNRL process was considered as a dependent variable. Linear and quadratic models were adjusted to the experimental results, which were obtained from a factorial design.

Experimental Procedure

Formulation

The latex used in this investigation was high ammonia (0.7%) NR latex. The sensitizer

was n-BA GR, and a 10% KOH GR solution was used to stabilize the latex. The analytical methods used to characterize the latex were in accordance with ASTM D 1076-79. The total solids content was $61.6 \pm 0.1\%$ and the dry rubber content was $60.44 \pm 2.0\%$. The latex formulation methodology was as follows [Sumarno and Sundardi, 1977]: NR latex was mixed with KOH to increase its chemical stability and this mixture was then mixed with n-BA. The latex-KOH mixture was constantly stirred while n-BA was added to it. Samples of this mixed latex were separated and left undisturbed for 16h.

Irradiation

Irradiation was carried out using gamma rays from a panoramic Cobalt-60 source at room temperature without disturbing the position of the mixed latex samples. The VD studied were 10, 15 and 20 kGy and the DR controlled at 0.07, 0.21 and 2.22 kGy h^{-1} by varying the distance from the Co-60 source. These parameters were followed from literature.

Preparation of RVNRL plates

Soon after the irradiation was carried out, 2mm thick rubber plates were produced by casting latex samples at room temperature in glass plates, with surface area of 125cm^2 and volume of 125mL. The film casting time (72 hours) depended on the rubber plate thickness, temperature and humidity. The rubber plate was firm enough to be taken out of the glass plate and leached in water (343°K) for 2h to remove non-rubber components. At the end of the leaching period, the plates were dried in open air overnight at room temperature, before being finally dried in an oven at 343°K with air circulation, until fully transparent (duration about 2h).

Tensile strength testing

The plates when fully dried were removed from the oven and kept in a desiccator overnight. The plates were cut into dumbbell shaped specimens for the tensile tests, according to ASTM D-412-80 standard. The thickness determined was an average of three measurements, in the reduced test section of the specimens, with values within $\pm 3.7\%$. Three specimens were selected for each experimental condition. Tensile tests were carried out in a Instron Testing Machine equipped to stretch at $8.3 \pm 0.8 \text{ mm s}^{-1}$. The tests were carried out at 298°K .

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Evaluation was carried out utilizing Response Surface Methodology (RSM), a technique based on full factorial design with central points [Box; Hunter; Hunter 1978]. The response surface of crosslinking efficiency of the latex vulcanized with gamma rays in the presence of n-BA was studied as a function of the processing conditions, obtained when one-factor-at-a-time method was used. There are three variables which influence the crosslinking efficiency in the RVNRL process: the VD, the DR and the concentration ratio of the sensitizer system [n-BA]/[KOH].

The tensile strength (Tb) is defined as the maximum tensile stress reached by the specimen at rupture. This is the physical property of vulcanized latex films, determined to evaluate the extent of crosslinking as a function of process parameters. The RVNRL process has been studied with the process parameters varying within the following intervals: [n-BA]/[KOH], (5/0.33), (1/0.0667) and (3/0.2) phr; VD 10, 15 and 20 kGy and DR 0.07, 0.21, 2.22 kGy h⁻¹. There are no significant differences in this property with the use of different vulcanizates (Table 1). This shows that it is possible to optimize the sensitizer system without significantly affecting the property of the final vulcanizate.

First order response surface design for 3 factors

The full factorial design (2³) with replicated central point (Table 1) comprised of 10 experimental conditions carried out randomly and distributed as follows: the first eight experimental conditions correspond to 2³ design; whereas the last two were duplicates of experimental conditions carried out at the central point. The last column in Table 1 shows the response variable results, Tb, obtained for each experimental condition from triplicate measure. The levels of the three variables were adjusted to account for industrial conditions. The codified variables (x₁, x₂, and x₃) were obtained in accordance with equations 1, 2 and 3 respectively.

$$x_1 = \frac{\left(\frac{[n-BA]}{[KOH]} - \frac{3}{0.2}\right)}{2} \quad (1)$$

$$x_2 = \frac{(VD - 15)}{5} \quad (2)$$

$$x_3 = \frac{(DR - 1.145)}{1.075} \quad (3)$$

The existence of three levels for each variable suggests the possibility of verifying whether there is lack of fit in the analyzed model or not. The response surface in this region was considered to be a linear function. Thus Tb (\hat{y}) could be estimated by equation (4), where b₀, b₁, b₂ and b₃ were the estimated parameters.

$$\hat{y} = b_0 + b_1x_1 + b_2x_2 + b_3x_3 \quad (4)$$

The experimental error (±0.072MPa) found in the first experiment was calculated with duplicate values in the central point experimental condition. The linear model parameters (b₀, b₁, b₂ and b₃) were estimated fitted by least squares method and the respective variances were calculated by the experimental error variance estimate, leading to the 5.

$$\hat{y} = 19.6 + 2.7x_1 + 0.7x_2 - 0.003x_3 \quad (5)$$

$\left(\pm 4.0\right)$ $\left(\pm 0.3\right)$ $\left(\pm 0.3\right)$ $\left(\pm 0.3\right)$

The analysis of variance (Table 2) for the fitted equation (5) showed that the correlation coefficient (squared for model) (R²) was (60.64/141.88 = 42.7%), and the pure experimental error contribution (R²-adj) was (141.88-0.006/141.88 = 99.9%). This showed that the linear model did not adapt to the experimental data (Table 1). Therefore, there was a clear evidence of the lack of fit, which was confirmed by the high ratio 16.25/0.006 = 2,685.6.

Mean effects and two-factor interaction effects.

The analysis of mean effects and two-factor interaction effects (Table 3) showed that there was high n-BA concentration effect, increasing Tb (5.4 ± 0.3MPa). This variable could not be considered separately as it interacted with VD.

The graphic representation of this interaction shows non-parallel straight lines (Figure 1) corroborating the results in which the factors interact. This interaction took place due to differences in sensitivity of Tb with respect to [n-BA] variation for the two levels of the VD; i.e. Tb is less sensitive to [n-BA] with high VD (20kGy), whereas the [n-BA] effect is higher (8MPa) with low VD (19kGy). This proves that irradiation inhibits crosslinking efficiency due to n-BA in the RVNRL process, which was optimized with low VD and high levels of [n-BA].

The influence of effects (Table 3) shows that DR did not have a noticeable effect over crosslinking efficiency within the experimental interval considered here. Therefore in

subsequent experiments higher DR levels (used in industrial processes) were considered. In accordance with Puig's research (1971), which reported that DR did not influence the crosslinking efficiency when the latex was irradiated with gamma rays, we observed similar behavior. However, when the sensitized latex was irradiated with electrons, it was greatly affected by DR (Chen, 1990), due to differences in the DR levels (10^4 times).

The presence of curvature in the experimental region is quite significant ($p=0.012<0.05$) as it indicates that optimal operational condition is close, but the factorial design used was not adequate to find this point accurately. Therefore, the factorial design was widened, producing the compound central design. The next step was to approximate the data to a quadratic model, taking only two variables ([n-BA]/[KOH] and VD) into consideration and fixing the DR at 0.70 kGy h^{-1} . Second order response surface design for 2 factors

The quadratic model for 2 variables is represented as follows:

$$\hat{y} = b_0 + b_1x_1 + b_2x_2 + b_3x_1^2 + b_4x_2^2 + b_5x_1x_2 \quad (6)$$

However, this model has six parameters. This implies that a compound central design will be adopted. The new points in the design matrix variables (Table 4) that are $\sqrt{2}$ distance from the central point were calculated. Moreover, the planned experimental conditions are shown in the last four lines of Table 4.

The first five experimental conditions of Table 4 belong to the first matrix of experimental conditions, (Table 1) taken to complete the compound central design. The experimental error $\square 1.05\text{MPa}$ and the compound experimental error $\square 0.18\text{MPa}$ were calculated from three additional replicas, which are found in the central point (run: 11, 12 and 13). The quadratic model parameters (b_0 , b_1 , b_2 , b_3 , and b_4 e b_5) were estimated fitting by the least square line methods and the variances were calculated with the experimental error variance estimate. The fitted equation 7 was thus obtained:

$$\hat{y} = 22.1 + 2.2x_1 + 1.1x_2 - 4.3x_1^2 - 1.4x_2^2 - 0.8x_1x_2 \quad (7)$$

(± 0.7) (± 0.9) (± 0.9) (± 1.0) (± 1.0) (± 1.2)

The variance analysis (Table 5) for adjusting the quadratic model of the experimental data from Table 4 shows the ratio

$12.29/4.13 = 2.98$. There is no evidence regarding the quadratic model's lack of fit.

Despite the fact that R^2 is 77.2% and R^2 -adj is 94.3%, the model is 90% reliable. At reliability of 75%, the model is both meaningful and useful for estimates. The graphic representation contours of fitted second order (Figure 2) and response surface (Figure 3) show the optimal region. To have the model maximized (Equation 7) with respect to $(\frac{\partial \hat{y}}{\partial x_1} = 0$

and $\frac{\partial \hat{y}}{\partial x_2} = 0$), the following optimal operational conditions were obtained, when $x_1 = 0.22$, to correspond to $[n\text{-BA}]/[\text{KOH}] = 2.56\text{phr} / 0.17\text{phr}$ and $x_2 = 0.32$ to correspond to $\text{VD} = 16.61\text{kGy}$. The T_b obtained in this condition was 22.54 MPa.

The concentration ratio value was always 15 and Equation 7 could be written as:

$$\hat{y} = -3.43 + 7.52[n\text{-BA}] - 1.07[n\text{-BA}]^2 + 1.68(\text{VD}) - 0.056(\text{VD})^2 \quad (8)$$

where the units of n-BA was phr and the units of VD was kGy.

Conclusion

The results obtained show that T_b was not affected by radiation dose rate in the experimental range ($0.07\text{-}2.22 \text{ kGy h}^{-1}$). However, the vulcanization dose and the concentration ratio of sensitizer system ($[n\text{-BA}]/[\text{KOH}]$) affected the crosslinking efficiency and they interacted. The vulcanization dose decreased with increasing n-BA concentration. Due to this interaction effect, the parameters of the process could be optimized at high concentration of n-BA and low vulcanization dose. The effect of concentration of n-BA on T_b was minor at 20kGy and 10kGy vulcanization doses. It can be concluded that radiation inhibits the n-BA participation in the crosslinking process of latex.

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Figure 1: Graphic representation of [n-BA] and vulcanization dose interaction.

Figure 2: Contours of fitted quadratic model.

Figure 3: Surface response of fitted quadratic model.

Table 1 – Results of the first-order response surface experimental design for 3 factors.

[nBA]/[KOH] (phr)	VD (kGy)	DR (kGy h ⁻¹)	Design matrix variables			Tb (MPa)
			X ₁	X ₂	X ₃	
1/0.0667	10	0.07	-1	-1	-1	13.22 ± 2.57
5/0.3333	10	0.07	1	-1	-1	20.98 ± 0.66
1/0.0667	20	0.07	-1	1	-1	17.24 ± 0.30
5/0.3333	20	0.07	1	1	-1	21.95 ± 0.40
1/0.0667	10	2.22	-1	-1	1	14.37 ± 0.82
5/0.3333	10	2.22	1	-1	1	22.06 ± 0.42
1/0.0667	20	2.22	-1	1	1	17.88 ± 0.54
5/0.3333	20	2.22	1	1	1	19.05 ± 1.85
3/0.2	15	0,21	0	0	0	24.73 ± 0.68
3/0.2	15	0,21	0	0	0	24.62 ± 1.11

n-BA: n-butyl acrylate; VD: Vulcanization dose; DR Irradiation dose rate; Tb: Tensile strength at rupture; x₁, x₂, x₃: Coded variables.

Table 2 – Analysis of variance for linear model.

Source	Sum of squares	Degrees of freedom	Mean square
Model	60.6385	3	20.2128
Residual	81.2441	6	13.5407
Lack of fit	81.2381	5	16.2476
Pure error	0.0060	1	0.0060
Total	141.8827	9	

Table 3 – Analysis of variance of mean and two-factor interaction effects.

Effects	Parameters	Standard deviation	Significance
Curvature check	-6.3	0.69	0.012
1:[nBA]/[KOH]	2.7	0.31	0.013
2: VD	0.7	0.31	0.156
3: DR	-0.003	0.31	0.993
Interaction 12	-1.2	0.31	0.060
Interaction 13	-0.5	0.31	0.280
Interaction 23	-0.6	0.31	0.209

n-BA: n-butyl acrylate; VD: Vulcanization dose; DR Irradiation dose rate.

Table 4 – Results of second-order response surface experimental design for 2 factors.

[n-BA]/[KOH] (phr)	VD (kGy)	Design matrix variables		Tb (MPa)
		x ₁	x ₂	
1/0.07	10	-1	-1	13.22 ± 2.57
5/0.33	10	1	-1	20.98 ± 0.66
1/0.07	20	-1	1	17.24 ± 0.30
5/0.33	20	1	1	21.95 ± 0.40
3/0.2	15	0	0	24.62 ± 1.16
3/0.2	15	0	0	19.72 ± 0.54
3/0.2	15	0	0	21.66 ± 0.27
3/0.2	15	0	0	22.55 ± 0.33
0.17/0.01	15	$-\sqrt{2}$	0	09.96 ± 0.79
5.83/0.39	15	$\sqrt{2}$	0	13.31 ± 0.65
3/0.2	7	0	$-\sqrt{2}$	16.17 ± 0.36
3/0.2	23	0	$\sqrt{2}$	18.68 ± 0.64

n-BA: n-butyl acrylate; VD: Vulcanization dose; Tb: Tensile strength at rupture; x₁, x₂: Coded variables.

Table 5 - Analysis of variance for quadratic model.

Source	Sum of squares	Degrees of freedom	Mean square
Model	168.58	5	33.72
Residual	49.29	6	8.21
Lack of fit	36.88	3	12.29
Pure error	12.41	3	4.13
Total	217.87	11	